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An inverse problem for Bingham type fluids[☆]

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we study a coefficient identification problem described by an elliptic variational-hemivariational inequality with unilateral constraints. The inequality is the weak formulation of the mathematical model of a stationary incompressible flow of Bingham type in a bounded domain. The unknown coefficient is a generalized viscosity function of the fluid. The boundary conditions represent generalizations of the no leak condition and a multivalued and nonmonotone version of a nonlinear Navier–Fujita frictional slip condition. The result on well posedness of the direct problem is established based on the theory of multivalued pseudomonotone operators. The existence to the inverse problem is proved by a Weierstrass type argument.

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1. Introduction

Much of the modelling on non-Newtonian fluids concentrates on finding a tensorial constitutive relation $\mathbb{S} = \mathbb{S}(\mathbb{D})$ between the deviatoric stress tensor \mathbb{S} and the rate deformation tensor $\mathbb{D} = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)$, where \mathbf{u} stands for the fluid velocity, see [1–3], and we distinguish between compressible and incompressible fluid. For most of the non-Newtonian fluids, the relation between stress and deformation is modelled by the equation

$$\mathbb{S} = 2\mu(\dot{\gamma})\mathbb{D},$$

where a generalized viscosity μ depends nonlinearly only on the first principal invariant $\dot{\gamma}$ defined by $\dot{\gamma} = \sqrt{2\mathbb{D} : \mathbb{D}}$. In particular, for a Newtonian fluid we have a linear relation $\mathbb{S} = 2\mu_0\mathbb{D}$, where $\mu_0 > 0$ is a given viscosity constant of the fluid.

The non-Newtonian models were developed to fit experimental data and the form of $\mu(\dot{\gamma})$ is usually derived experimentally. Several empirical relations between μ and $\dot{\gamma}$ have been suggested. Some common expressions used

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to fit data are the power law model, the Carreau–Yasuda model, the Cross model, Herschel–Bulkley model, the yield fluid models, and others, see [4] and the references therein. Note that a Carreau type fluid is currently a more broadly applicable model than the power-law model, see [4]. However, many fluids are still too nonlinear to be described by the aforementioned models. For these fluids there are no exact solutions or exact approximations, and other models have to be considered.

In this paper, being motivated by the necessity to improve a theoretical model of a real system, we provide a mathematical analysis of an identification problem. The latter is an inverse coefficient problem which consists in the determination of the unknown nonlinear viscosity coefficient μ from a class \mathcal{M}_{ad} of admissible coefficients in the stationary Stokes model of an incompressible fluid of Bingham type in a bounded domain from various “measured” data. For example, the measured data may consist of the Dirichlet-type data $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}_d$ on Γ_a measured on an “accessible” part Γ_a of the boundary such that $\Gamma_a \cap \Gamma_0 = \emptyset$. The approach is based on an optimal control technique to minimize a cost functional over the admissible set of coefficients. For instance, we can use the popular least-square method and deal with the cost of the form

$$\min_{\mu \in \mathcal{M}_{ad}} \int_{\Gamma_a} \|\mathbf{u}(\mu) - \mathbf{u}_d\|^2 d\Gamma, \tag{1}$$

where $\mathbf{u}(\mu)$ represents the unique solution of the direct problem (the nonlinear Stokes model).

The novelties of the paper are as follows. First, a direct problem is described by a novel type of variational–hemivariational inequalities with constraints. The model is treated with mixed boundary conditions that allow to capture various phenomena at the surface of contact between a non-Newtonian fluid and the boundary of the domain. To the best of the authors knowledge, up to now, there has not been any study on the Bingham type flow with nonmonotone multivalued boundary conditions. Although the inequality is nonstandard, its particular cases are of great interest. This is the case of a nonmonotone and multivalued boundary condition that generalizes a nonlinear Navier–Fujita frictional slip condition. Second, we provide a result on the well-posedness of the direct problem. The weak unique solvability of the problem and the continuity of the control-to-state map $\mu \mapsto \mathbf{u}(\mu)$ are crucial for the existence of solution to the inverse problem. Third, we prove the existence of solution to a class of inverse problems which include several possible objective functionals. Moreover, the model comprises the multivalued boundary condition (6) involving a nonlinearity of the form $k \partial j$. This kind of nonlinearity cannot be generally represented by a purely hemivariational inequality since there is no potential G such that $\partial G = k \partial j$. This type of nonlinearity leads to a “hemivariational term” on the boundary in the inequality while the Bingham law leads to a “variational part” in the domain.

The mathematical model we consider was first suggested by Bingham [5] in 1916. There are plenty of real substances such as mineral suspensions, adhesives like wall paper paste, wet beach sand, polymer melts and solutions, biological fluids like blood in the capillaries, coal slurries, fire fighting foams, etc. which can be described by the Bingham model. The system of partial differential equations involving the Bingham constitutive law has been studied in many papers, for instance, in Duvaut and Lions in [6, Chapter VI], where the existence of weak solutions is demonstrated, and in [7,8] for frictional problems. More recently, the stationary Bingham model has been examined in [9] by using a mixed variational formulation with Lagrange multipliers and in [10] by the variational inequality formulation that uses the abstract result of Lions [11, Theorem 8.5, p.251]. Several classes of variational–hemivariational inequalities have been successfully used for various fluid models in [12–16]. Inverse problems for variational and hemivariational inequalities can be found in [17,18], respectively. Further, numerical optimization gradient methods and simulations have been proposed in [19] to identify some rheological parameters of a non-Newtonian fluid. Certain methodologies to identify the viscosity of non-Newtonian fluids include a nonlinear least-squares method, genetic algorithms, and the particle swarm optimization, and the collage theorem, among others, see, e.g., [4,20]. In a more general context, including the use of the collage theorem, the related studies can be found in [21–24]. The future work is planned on the numerical analysis of the inverse problem to determine the viscosity function. To this end, we clearly need an effective numerical algorithm to solve the variational–hemivariational inequality.

The paper is structured as follows. The notation and basic definitions are recalled in Section 2. In Section 3, we give the classical setting and a variational formulation of the mathematical model of the incompressible Bingham type fluid. The main theorem on the well-posedness of the direct problem is established in Section 4. In Section 5 a result on solvability of an inverse coefficient problem is obtained. Finally, Section 6 suggests some open problems for future work.

2. Mathematical preliminaries

In this section we set up notation and terminology, and recall some results that will be used in what follows, see [25–29].

Let $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ be a normed space. Throughout the paper, X^* denotes the dual of X and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{X^* \times X}$ is the duality brackets for the pair (X^*, X) . With “ \rightharpoonup ” and “ \rightarrow ” we denote the weak and norm convergences, respectively. Given a set $D \subset X$, we write $\|D\|_X = \sup\{\|x\|_X \mid x \in D\}$. For simplicity, when no confusion arises, we often skip the subscripts.

Let X be a Banach space. For a multivalued operator $T : X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$, its domain $D(T)$ and graph $Gr(T)$ are defined, respectively, by $D(T) = \{x \in X \mid Tx \neq \emptyset\}$, $Gr(T) = \{(x, x^*) \in X \times X^* \mid x^* \in Tx\}$. Recall that if $T_1, T_2 : X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$, then $D(T_1 + T_2) = D(T_1) \cap D(T_2)$. An operator $T : X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$ is called monotone when $\langle u^* - v^*, u - v \rangle \geq 0$ for all $(u, u^*), (v, v^*) \in Gr(T)$.

$(v, v^*) \in Gr(T)$. It is said to be maximal monotone, if it is monotone and maximal in the sense of inclusion of graphs in the family of monotone operators from X to 2^{X^*} . Given $u_0 \in X$, T is said to be u_0 -coercive, if there exists a function $\alpha : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $\lim_{r \rightarrow +\infty} \alpha(r) = +\infty$ such that for all $(u, u^*) \in Gr(T)$, we have $\langle u^*, u - u_0 \rangle \geq \alpha(\|u\|) \|u\|$. An operator T is bounded, if T maps bounded sets of X into bounded sets of X^* .

Let X be a reflexive Banach space. An operator $T : X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$ is pseudomonotone if:

- (a) for every $u \in X$, the set $Tu \subset X^*$ is nonempty, closed and convex,
- (b) T is upper semicontinuous from each finite dimensional subspace of X into X^* endowed with weak topology,
- (c) for all sequences $\{u_n\} \subset X$ and $\{u_n^*\} \subset X^*$ such that $u_n \rightharpoonup u$ in X , $u_n^* \in Tu_n$ for all $n \geq 1$ and $\limsup \langle u_n^*, u_n - u \rangle \leq 0$, we have that for every $v \in X$, there exists $u^*(v) \in Tu$ such that $\langle u^*(v), u - v \rangle \leq \liminf \langle u_n^*, u_n - v \rangle$.

An operator $T : X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$ is generalized pseudomonotone if for any sequences $\{u_n\} \subset X$ and $\{u_n^*\} \subset X^*$ such that $u_n \rightharpoonup u$ in X , $u_n^* \in Tu_n$ for $n \geq 1$, $u_n^* \rightharpoonup u^*$ in X^* and $\limsup \langle u_n^*, u_n - u \rangle \leq 0$, we have $u^* \in Tu$ and $\lim \langle u_n^*, u_n \rangle = \langle u^*, u \rangle$. It is known that if T is pseudomonotone, then it is generalized pseudomonotone. If T is a bounded generalized pseudomonotone operator such that for all $u \in X$, Tu is a nonempty, closed and convex subset of X^* , then T is pseudomonotone.

Given $u_0 \in X$ and $T : X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$, a multivalued operator T_{u_0} is defined by $T_{u_0}(v) = T(v + u_0)$ for all $v \in X$. We recall a surjectivity result needed in next sections.

Theorem 1 ([29, Theorem 2.12]). *Let X be a reflexive Banach space, $T_1 : X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$ a pseudomonotone operator and $T_2 : X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$ a maximal monotone operator, and $u_0 \in D(T_2)$. Assume that T_1 is u_0 -coercive, and either T_{1u_0} or T_{2u_0} is bounded. Then $T_1 + T_2$ is surjective.*

Let X be a Banach space. An operator $A : X \rightarrow X^*$ is said to be monotone, if for all $u, v \in X$, it holds $\langle Au - Av, u - v \rangle \geq 0$. It is called maximal monotone, if it is monotone, and $\langle Au - w, u - v \rangle \geq 0$ for any $u \in X$ entails $w = Av$. Operator A is called pseudomonotone, if it is bounded and $u_n \rightharpoonup u$ in X with $\limsup \langle Au_n, u_n - u \rangle \leq 0$ imply $\langle Au, u - v \rangle \leq \liminf \langle Au_n, u_n - v \rangle$ for all $v \in X$. It is known that if X is a reflexive Banach space, then $A : X \rightarrow X^*$ is pseudomonotone, if and only if it is bounded and $u_n \rightharpoonup u$ in X with $\limsup \langle Au_n, u_n - u \rangle \leq 0$ imply $\lim \langle Au_n, u_n - u \rangle = 0$ and $Au_n \rightharpoonup Au$ in X^* .

Let X be a Banach space and $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be a proper, convex and lower semicontinuous function. The mapping $\partial\varphi : X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$ defined by

$$\partial\varphi(x) = \{x^* \in X^* \mid \langle x^*, v - x \rangle \leq \varphi(v) - \varphi(x) \text{ for all } v \in X\}$$

is called the (convex) subdifferential of φ and an element $x^* \in \partial\varphi(x)$ is called a subgradient of φ at x . Let $h : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a locally Lipschitz function. The generalized (Clarke) directional derivative of h at the point $x \in X$ in the direction $v \in X$ is defined by

$$h^0(x; v) = \limsup_{y \rightarrow x, \lambda \downarrow 0} \frac{h(y + \lambda v) - h(y)}{\lambda}.$$

The generalized subgradient of h at x is a subset of the dual space X^* given by

$$\partial h(x) = \{\zeta \in X^* \mid h^0(x; v) \geq \langle \zeta, v \rangle \text{ for all } v \in X\}.$$

3. An incompressible Bingham type model

Let Ω be a bounded open connected set in \mathbb{R}^d with a Lipschitz boundary Γ . The set Ω is occupied by the incompressible Bingham fluid for $d = 2$ and $d = 3$. The boundary Γ consists of three smooth parts Γ_0, Γ_1 and Γ_2 such that $|\Gamma_0| > 0$.

The classical (strong) formulation of the steady-state flow problem reads as follows.

Problem 2. Find a flow velocity $\mathbf{u} : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$, an extra stress tensor $\mathbb{S} : \mathbb{M}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{M}^d$, and a pressure $p : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$-\text{Div } \mathbb{S} + \nabla p = \mathbf{f} \quad \text{in } \Omega, \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{cases} \mathbb{S} = \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} + g \frac{\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|} & \text{if } \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} \neq \mathbf{0} \\ \|\mathbb{S}\| \leq g & \text{if } \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} \end{cases} \quad \text{in } \Omega, \tag{3}$$

$$\text{div } \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega, \tag{4}$$

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0} \quad \text{on } \Gamma_0, \tag{5}$$

$$\begin{cases} u_\nu = 0 \\ -\boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \in k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|) \partial j(\mathbf{u}_\tau) \end{cases} \quad \text{on } \Gamma_1. \tag{6}$$

$$\begin{cases} u_\nu + g_0 \geq 0, \boldsymbol{\tau}_\nu(\mathbf{u}, p) + h(u_\nu) \geq 0 \\ (u_\nu + g_0)(\boldsymbol{\tau}_\nu(\mathbf{u}, p) + h(u_\nu)) = 0 \\ \boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) = 0 \end{cases} \quad \text{on } \Gamma_2, \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{cases} -\boldsymbol{\tau}_\nu(\mathbf{u}, \pi) \in \partial\phi(u_\nu) \\ \mathbf{u}_\tau = 0 \end{cases} \quad \text{on } \Gamma_3. \tag{8}$$

Here and in what follows, we use the following notation. Let \mathbb{M}^d be the class of symmetric $d \times d$ matrices. The traction vector is denoted by $\boldsymbol{\tau}(\mathbf{u}, p) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}, p)\boldsymbol{\nu}$ on Γ , where total stress tensor is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{u}, p) = -p\mathbb{I} + \mathbb{S}(\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}) \quad \text{in } \Omega,$$

where the unit outward normal vector on boundary is denoted by $\boldsymbol{\nu}$, and \mathbb{I} is the identity $d \times d$ matrix. The normal and tangential components of the traction vector and of the displacement field on the boundary are defined by $\tau_\nu(\mathbf{u}, p) = \boldsymbol{\tau}(\mathbf{u}, p) \cdot \boldsymbol{\nu}$, $\boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) = \boldsymbol{\tau}(\mathbf{u}, p) - \tau_\nu(\mathbf{u}, p)\boldsymbol{\nu}$, and by $u_\nu = \mathbf{u} \cdot \boldsymbol{\nu}$, $\mathbf{u}_\tau = \mathbf{u} - u_\nu\boldsymbol{\nu}$, respectively. Moreover, we have

$$\mathbb{S}_\nu(\mathbf{u}) = \tau_\nu(\mathbf{u}, p) + p, \quad \mathbb{S}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) = \boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \quad \text{on } \Gamma. \tag{9}$$

Remark that $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ and τ_ν do depend on the pressure p , and $\boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau$ is independent of p .

The notation Div and div stand for the divergence operators for tensor and vector valued functions $\mathbb{S}: \mathbb{M}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{M}^d$ and $\mathbf{u}: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ defined by $\text{Div } \mathbb{S} = (S_{ij,j})$ and $\text{div } \mathbf{u} = (u_{i,i})$, and the index that follows a comma represents the partial derivative with respect to the corresponding component of \mathbf{x} . To simplify the notation, we often do not indicate explicitly the dependence of various functions on the spatial variable $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega \cup \Gamma$. The inner products and norms on \mathbb{R}^d and \mathbb{M}^d are denoted by the intuitive notation, and very often the subscripts are omitted.

The Stokes equation (2) represents the conservation law, where \mathbf{f} is the volume density of given forces. The constitutive law of the Bingham fluid given by (3) is a relation between the extra stress tensor \mathbb{S} and the strain velocity tensor $\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}$ whose components are given by

$$\mathbb{D}_{ij}(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad \text{for } \mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_d),$$

μ stands for the viscosity coefficient, and g for the plasticity threshold (yield stress). It states that the norm of the extra stress is limited by a maximal value g called the yield limit (or plasticity threshold). If the strict inequality is satisfied (the stress is low), there are no deformations and the fluid behave as a rigid body, when equality holds (at high stress), then the body initiates to behave as a fluid. Examples of Bingham fluids include cosmetics and personal care products, water suspensions of clay, drilling muds, volcanic lava and magmas, or sewage sludge. For $g = 0$ and $\mu(r) = \mu_0$, the constitutive law reduces to the model of Newtonian fluid for the Navier–Stokes equation. The incompressibility of the fluid is expressed by the solenoidal (divergence free) condition (4). The homogeneous Dirichlet boundary condition (5) means that the fluid adheres to the wall, see [28].

The multivalued boundary condition (6) describes a generalization of the Navier–Fujita slip condition. It is motivated by models of flows of polymer melts during extrusion, flows of Newtonian fluids with a moving contact line, and flows of yield-stress fluids, etc. The condition $u_\nu = 0$ on Γ_1 is called the impermeability (no leak) boundary condition. The second condition in (6) generalizes three slip boundary conditions: the Navier slip condition in [30] (stating that the tangential velocity \mathbf{u}_τ is proportional to the shear stress $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_\tau$), the nonlinear Navier-type slip condition in [31], and the threshold slip condition of frictional type studied in a series of papers by Fujita et al. [32–36]. The condition (6) is much more general than slip conditions in the aforementioned papers. It involves models with nonmonotone slip boundary condition of frictional type governed by nonconvex locally Lipschitz superpotentials j , for concrete examples, see [15, Example (60)], and the references therein.

The unilateral condition (7) has been recently suggested and studied in [37] to model a new outflow unilateral boundary condition for blood flow simulations. It has an advantage over the popular do-nothing boundary condition. In (7), g_0 is a given positive constant and h is a prescribed nonnegative function. It is a counterpart of the Signorini-type condition which models the unilateral contact in the theory of elasticity. Moreover, condition (7) has been studied for the Stokes problem in [38] with $h(\mathbf{x}, r) = h(\mathbf{x})$, and recently in [15]. The boundary condition (8) is called the generalized leak boundary condition of frictional type. It describes lack of slip on the boundary Γ_3 and a possible leakage of the fluid through this part of the boundary with a prescribed convex function ϕ . For the choice $\phi(r) = |r|$ for $r \in \mathbb{R}$ and further discussion, we refer to [15].

To obtain the weak formulation of Problem 2, we need the following spaces.

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{V} &= \{ \mathbf{v} \in C^\infty(\overline{\Omega}; \mathbb{R}^d) \mid \text{div } \mathbf{v} = 0 \text{ in } \Omega, \mathbf{v} = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_0, v_\nu = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_1, \mathbf{v}_\tau = 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_3 \}, \\ V &= \text{closure of } \tilde{V} \text{ in } H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^d). \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

On the space V we consider two norms, the standard one $\|\mathbf{v}\| = \|\mathbf{v}\|_{H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^d)}$, and the norm given by $\|\mathbf{v}\|_V = \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\|_{L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{M}^d)}$ for $\mathbf{v} \in V$. It is known from the Korn inequality, see, e.g., [12, Theorem 8], that $\|\cdot\|_{H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^d)}$ and $\|\cdot\|_V$ are equivalent norms on V . Let $H = L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^d)$ and

$$K = \{ \mathbf{v} \in V \mid v_\nu + g_0 \geq 0 \text{ on } \Gamma_2 \} \quad \text{with a constant } g_0 > 0 \tag{11}$$

be the set of unilateral constraints for Problem 2. The trace operator is denoted by

$$\gamma: V \subset H^1(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^d) \rightarrow L^2(\Gamma; \mathbb{R}^d). \tag{12}$$

It is well known, see [26, Chapter 3.9], that it is a linear, continuous and compact operator. Moreover, instead of $\gamma\mathbf{v}$, for simplicity, we often write \mathbf{v} . We denote its norm in the space $\mathcal{L}(V, L^2(\Gamma; \mathbb{R}^d))$ by $\|\gamma\|$.

We need the following hypotheses on the data.

$H(\mu)$: $\mu: [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function such that

- (i) $\mu \in C([0, \infty); \mathbb{R})$, $0 < \mu_0 \leq \mu(r) \leq \mu_1$ for all $r \in [0, \infty)$,
- (ii) $(\mu(\|\mathbf{A}\|)\mathbf{A} - \mu(\|\mathbf{B}\|)\mathbf{B}) : (\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}) \geq \mu_2 \|\mathbf{A} - \mathbf{B}\|^2$ for all $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{M}^d$ with $\mu_2 > 0$.

$H(f, g)$: $\mathbf{f} \in H, g \in L^2(\Omega), g \geq 0$.

$H(h)$: $h: \Gamma_2 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function such that

- (i) $h(\cdot, r)$ is measurable for all $r \in \mathbb{R}$,
- (ii) $h(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$ is continuous and nondecreasing for a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_2$,
- (iii) $0 \leq h(\mathbf{x}, r) \leq h_0$ for all $r \in \mathbb{R}$ and a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_2$,
- (iv) $h(\mathbf{x}, 0) = 0$ for a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_2$.

$H(j)$: $j: \Gamma_1 \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function such that

- (i) $j(\cdot, \boldsymbol{\xi})$ is measurable on Γ_1 for all $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathbb{R}^d$,
- (ii) $j(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$ is locally Lipschitz for a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$,
- (iii) $\|\partial j(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\xi})\|_{\mathbb{R}^d} \leq c_0(\mathbf{x}) + c_1 \|\boldsymbol{\xi}\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}$ for all $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$ with $c_0 \in L^2(\Gamma_1), c_0, c_1 \geq 0$,
- (iv) there exists $m_j \geq 0$ such that $j^0(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\xi}_1; \boldsymbol{\xi}_2 - \boldsymbol{\xi}_1) + j^0(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\xi}_2; \boldsymbol{\xi}_1 - \boldsymbol{\xi}_2) \leq m_j \|\boldsymbol{\xi}_1 - \boldsymbol{\xi}_2\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}^2$ for all $\boldsymbol{\xi}_1, \boldsymbol{\xi}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^d$, a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$.

$H(k)$: $k: \Gamma_1 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function such that

- (i) $k(\cdot, r)$ is measurable on Γ_1 for all $r \in \mathbb{R}$,
- (ii) $k(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$ is continuous on \mathbb{R} for a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$,
- (iii) $0 < k_0 \leq k(\mathbf{x}, r) \leq k_1$ for all $r \in \mathbb{R}$, a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$.

$H(\phi)$: $\phi: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is convex and lower semicontinuous.

Note that the Carreau-type and power-law models, popular among rheologists, could serve as examples for hypothesis $H(\mu)$. Such models are used in several areas of engineering sciences, mainly in chemical engineering, glaciology, colloidal mechanics, geology and blood rheology, see [3]. For instance, a typical example is the Carreau law of the form

$$\mu(t) = \mu_\infty + (\mu_0 - \mu_\infty)(1 + \lambda t^2)^{\frac{r-2}{2}} \text{ for } t \geq 0,$$

with $\lambda > 0, 1 < r \leq 2$ and $0 < \mu_\infty < \mu_0$. This function satisfies $\mu \in C^1([0, +\infty))$ and

$$\mu_\infty(t - s) \leq \mu(t)t - \mu(s)s \leq \mu_0(t - s) \text{ for all } t \geq s \geq 0. \tag{13}$$

It is known that if the viscosity μ satisfies (13), then $H(\mu)$ holds with suitable constants $\mu_0, \mu_1, \mu_2 > 0$, see [39, condition (2.3)] and [40, Lemma 2.1]. We note that the choice $r = 2$ leads to $\mu(t) = \mu_0$ which is the linear Newtonian constitutive relation (the Stokes system). Further, the hypothesis $H(\mu)(ii)$ is satisfied when μ is monotonically increasing, see [10, Remark 3].

The generalized gradient of j in hypothesis $H(j)(iii)$ is taken with respect to the second variable. Also, it is known that $H(j)(iv)$ is equivalent to the relaxed monotonicity of $\partial j(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$ for a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$ which has been widely used for hemivariational inequalities, see [28,41] and the references therein. If, in addition, the function $j(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$ is convex for all $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, then $H(j)(iv)$ holds with $m_j = 0$ due to the monotonicity of the convex subdifferential.

We now derive the variational formulation of Problem 2. We assume now that \mathbf{u}, \mathbb{S} and p are sufficiently smooth functions which satisfy (2)–(8). Let $\mathbf{v} \in K$. We multiply Eq. (2) by $\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}$ and integrate over Ω to obtain

$$\int_\Omega (-\text{Div } \mathbb{S}) \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx + \int_\Omega \nabla p \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx = \int_\Omega \mathbf{f} \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx. \tag{14}$$

For the first term on the left hand side of (14), we use the Green formula from [28, Theorems 2.24] to get

$$\int_\Omega (-\text{Div } \mathbb{S}) \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx = \int_\Omega \mathbb{S} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx - \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbb{S} \mathbf{v}) \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) d\Gamma.$$

The second term on the left hand side of (14) can be expressed by

$$\int_\Omega \nabla p \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx = \int_{\Gamma_2} (v_\nu - u_\nu) p d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_3} (v_\nu - u_\nu) p d\Gamma, \tag{15}$$

where we used the second Green-type formula, see [28, Theorem 2.25], and the properties $\text{div } \mathbf{u} = \text{div } \mathbf{v} = 0$ in Ω , $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{v} = 0$ on Γ_0 and $u_\nu = v_\nu = 0$ on Γ_1 .

Next, we use (9), the decomposition formula, see [28, relation (6.33)], and the condition $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{v} = 0$ on Γ_0 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbb{S} \mathbf{v}) \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) d\Gamma &= \int_{\Gamma_1} \mathbb{S}_v(\mathbf{u})(v_v - u_v) + \mathbb{S}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_2} \mathbb{S}_v(\mathbf{u})(v_v - u_v) \\ &+ \mathbb{S}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_3} \mathbb{S}_v(\mathbf{u})(v_v - u_v) + \mathbb{S}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma \\ &= \int_{\Gamma_1} \boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_2} (\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p) + p)(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma \\ &+ \int_{\Gamma_3} (\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p) + p)(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma = \int_{\Gamma_1} \boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma \\ &+ \int_{\Gamma_2} (\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p) + h(u_v))(v_v + g_0) - (\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p) + h(u_v))(g_0 + u_v) \\ &- h(u_v)(v_v - u_v) + p(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_3} (\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p) + p)(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma. \end{aligned}$$

Now, taking into account the relations, see (7),

$$(\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p) + h(u_v))(v_v + g_0) \geq 0, \quad (\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p) + h(u_v))(u_v + g_0) = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_2,$$

we infer that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\partial\Omega} (\mathbb{S} \mathbf{v}) \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) d\Gamma &\geq \int_{\Gamma_1} \boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma \\ &+ \int_{\Gamma_2} p(v_v - u_v) - h(u_v)(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_3} (\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p) + p)(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma. \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Therefore, combining (14), (15) and (16), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \mathbb{S} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx + \int_{\Gamma_2} (v_v - u_v)p d\Gamma \\ + \int_{\Gamma_3} (v_v - u_v)p d\Gamma &\geq \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx + \int_{\Gamma_1} \boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma \\ + \int_{\Gamma_2} p(v_v - u_v) - h(u_v)(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma &+ \int_{\Gamma_3} (\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p) + p)(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \mathbb{S} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx &\geq \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx + \int_{\Gamma_1} \boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma \\ - \int_{\Gamma_2} h(u_v)(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma &+ \int_{\Gamma_3} \tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p)(v_v - u_v) d\Gamma. \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

Now, we utilize (6) and (8) in the integrals over Γ_1 and Γ_3 , respectively. From the condition (6), $H(k)(iii)$ and the definition of the subgradient, it follows that $-\boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) = k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|)\boldsymbol{\xi}$ with $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \partial j(\mathbf{u}_\tau)$. Hence $\boldsymbol{\xi} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) \leq j^0(\mathbf{u}_\tau; \mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau)$ on Γ_1 and

$$-\boldsymbol{\tau}_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \cdot (\mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) \leq k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|)j^0(\mathbf{u}_\tau; \mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_1. \tag{18}$$

By condition (8), we have

$$-\tau_v(\mathbf{u}, p)(v_v - u_v) \leq \phi(v_v) - \phi(u_v) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_3. \tag{19}$$

Finally, we employ the constitutive relation (3). Let $\Omega_+ = \{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega \mid \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})\| > 0\}$ and $\Omega_0 = \{\mathbf{x} \in \Omega \mid \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})\| = 0\}$. From the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_+} \mathbb{S} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx &= \int_{\Omega_+} \left(\mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|)\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} + g \frac{\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|} \right) : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega_+} \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|)\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx + \int_{\Omega_+} g \frac{\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|} : \mathbb{D}\mathbf{v} dx - \int_{\Omega_+} g \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\| dx \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|)\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) dx + \int_{\Omega_+} g \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\| dx - \int_{\Omega} g \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\| dx. \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

On the other hand, by the condition $\|\mathbb{S}\| \leq g$ in Ω_0 , we have

$$\int_{\Omega_0} \mathbb{S} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) \, dx = \int_{\Omega_0} \mathbb{S} : \mathbb{D}\mathbf{v} \, dx \leq \int_{\Omega_0} \|\mathbb{S}\| \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\| \, dx \leq \int_{\Omega_0} g \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\| \, dx. \tag{21}$$

Adding the inequalities (20) and (21), we deduce

$$\int_{\Omega} \mathbb{S} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) \, dx \leq \int_{\Omega} \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|)\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) \, dx + \int_{\Omega} g (\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\| - \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \, dx. \tag{22}$$

We combine (17), (18), (19), and (22) and arrive at the following variational formulation of Problem 2.

Problem 3. Find a velocity $\mathbf{u} \in K$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|)\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) \, dx + \int_{\Gamma_2} h(u_\nu)(v_\nu - u_\nu) \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|)j^0(\mathbf{u}_\tau; \mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) \, d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_3} (\phi(v_\nu) - \phi(u_\nu)) \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\Omega} g (\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\| - \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \, dx \geq \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) \, dx \text{ for all } \mathbf{v} \in K. \end{aligned}$$

Problem 3 is called a nonlinear elliptic variational–hemivariational inequality with constraints. It is a direct problem for the inverse problem studied in Section 5. We will investigate the well-posedness of Problem 3 in the next section.

4. Main result on the direct problem

In what follows, we denote by \mathcal{M} the class of viscosity functions $\mu : [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which satisfy hypothesis $H(\mu)$.

Theorem 4. Assume hypotheses $H(\mu)$, $H(f, g)$, $H(h)$, $H(j)$, $H(k)$, and $H(\phi)$.

(i) If, in addition, the smallness condition

$$k_1 m_j \|\gamma\|^2 < \mu_2 \tag{23}$$

is satisfied, then Problem 3 has a solution.

(ii) If, in addition, the functions $j(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$ and $k(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$ are Lipschitz continuous for a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$ with constants $L_j, L_k > 0$, respectively, and

$$(k_1 m_j + L_j L_k) \|\gamma\|^2 < \mu_2 \tag{24}$$

holds, then the solution to Problem 3 is unique.

(iii) Assume hypotheses of (ii). Let $\{\mu_n\} \subset \mathcal{M}$ be a sequence of coefficients that satisfy uniformly with respect to $n \in \mathbb{N}$ conditions $H(\mu)$, and such that it converges pointwise in $[0, \infty)$ to a function $\mu \in \mathcal{M}$. Then the sequence $\{\mathbf{u}_n\} = \{\mathbf{u}(\mu_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ of unique solutions to Problem 3 corresponding to μ_n converges in V , as $n \rightarrow \infty$ to the solution $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}(\mu)$ of Problem 3 corresponding to μ .

Proof. (i) We begin with the proof of existence. Let $X = L^2(\Gamma_1; \mathbb{R}^d)$ and $Y = L^2(\Gamma_3)$. We introduce the following operators and functions defined by

$$A : V \rightarrow V^*, \quad \langle A\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle = \int_{\Omega} \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|)\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{D}\mathbf{v} \, dx + \int_{\Gamma_2} h(u_\nu) v_\nu \, d\Gamma, \quad \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in V, \tag{25}$$

$$J : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad J(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u}) = \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{w}\|)j(\mathbf{u}) \, d\Gamma, \quad \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u} \in X, \tag{26}$$

$$\Phi : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad \Phi(\mathbf{v}) = \int_{\Omega} g \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\| \, dx, \quad \mathbf{v} \in V, \tag{27}$$

$$\varphi : Y \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \quad \varphi(\eta) = \int_{\Gamma_3} \phi(\eta) \, d\Gamma, \quad \eta \in Y, \tag{28}$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{f}} \in V^*, \quad \langle \tilde{\mathbf{f}}, \mathbf{v} \rangle = \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot \mathbf{v} \, dx, \quad \mathbf{v} \in V, \tag{29}$$

$$M : V \rightarrow X, \quad N : V \rightarrow Y, \quad M\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}_\tau, \quad N\mathbf{v} = v_\nu, \quad \mathbf{v} \in V.$$

We shall use the notation above and write the variational–hemivariational inequality in [Problem 3](#) in an equivalent form: find $\mathbf{u} \in K$ such that

$$\langle \mathbf{A}\mathbf{u} - \tilde{\mathbf{f}}, \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u} \rangle + \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|)j^0(\mathbf{u}_\tau; \mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma + \Phi(\mathbf{v}) - \Phi(\mathbf{u}) + \varphi(N\mathbf{v}) - \varphi(N\mathbf{u}) \geq 0 \text{ for all } \mathbf{v} \in K. \tag{30}$$

In order to show existence of solution to [\(30\)](#), we consider the following operator inclusion.

Problem 5. Find $\mathbf{u} \in V$ such that

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{u} + M^*\partial J(M\mathbf{u}, M\mathbf{u}) + \partial\Phi(\mathbf{u}) + N^*\partial\varphi(N\mathbf{u}) + \partial I_K(\mathbf{u}) \ni \tilde{\mathbf{f}}.$$

In [Problem 5](#), the notation ∂J stands for the generalized subgradient of the function $J(\mathbf{w}, \cdot)$, and $\partial\Phi$, $\partial\varphi$ and ∂I_K denote the subdifferential in the sense of convex analysis of Φ , φ and I_K , respectively. Also, $M^*: X^* \rightarrow V^*$ and $N^*: Y^* \rightarrow V^*$ are the adjoint operators to M and N , respectively, and the indicator function of K , $I_K: V \rightarrow \{0, +\infty\}$, is defined by $I_K(\mathbf{v}) = 0$ if $\mathbf{v} \in K$, and $+\infty$, otherwise.

From $H(j)$ and [\[28, Theorem 3.47\(i\)–\(iv\)\]](#), it may be concluded that J is well defined on $X \times X$, $J(\mathbf{w}, \cdot)$ is Lipschitz on bounded subsets of X for any $\mathbf{w} \in X$ (and hence also locally Lipschitz on X), and the following inequality holds

$$J^0(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u}; \mathbf{v}) \leq \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{w}\|)j^0(\mathbf{u}; \mathbf{v}) d\Gamma, \quad \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in X. \tag{31}$$

We show that any solution of [Problem 5](#) is also a solution to problem [\(30\)](#). In fact, let $\mathbf{u} \in V$ be a solution of [Problem 5](#). We have

$$\mathbf{A}\mathbf{u} + M^*\xi + \eta + N^*\varrho + \zeta = \tilde{\mathbf{f}}, \tag{32}$$

where $\xi \in \partial J(M\mathbf{u}, M\mathbf{u})$, $\eta \in \partial\Phi(\mathbf{u})$, $\varrho \in \partial\varphi(N\mathbf{u})$, and $\zeta \in \partial I_K(\mathbf{u})$. By the definition of subgradients, it follows

$$\begin{cases} \langle \xi, \mathbf{z} \rangle_{X^* \times X} \leq J^0(M\mathbf{u}, M\mathbf{u}; \mathbf{z}) \text{ for all } \mathbf{z} \in X, \\ \langle \eta, \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u} \rangle \leq \Phi(\mathbf{v}) - \Phi(\mathbf{u}) \text{ for all } \mathbf{v} \in V, \\ \langle \varrho, \mathbf{z} - N\mathbf{u} \rangle_{Y^* \times Y} \leq \varphi(\mathbf{z}) - \varphi(N\mathbf{u}) \text{ for all } \mathbf{z} \in Y, \\ \langle \zeta, \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u} \rangle \leq I_K(\mathbf{v}) - I_K(\mathbf{u}) \text{ for all } \mathbf{v} \in V. \end{cases} \tag{33}$$

Let $\mathbf{v} \in V$. We multiply [\(32\)](#) by $\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}$ and use [\(33\)](#) to obtain

$$\langle \mathbf{A}\mathbf{u} + \eta + \zeta - \tilde{\mathbf{f}}, \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u} \rangle + \langle \xi, M(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) \rangle_{X^* \times X} + \langle \varrho, N\mathbf{v} - N\mathbf{u} \rangle_{Y^* \times Y} = 0. \tag{34}$$

We combine [\(34\)](#) with [\(31\)](#) and [\(33\)](#) to deduce

$$\langle \mathbf{A}\mathbf{u} - \tilde{\mathbf{f}}, \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u} \rangle + \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|)j^0(\mathbf{u}_\tau; \mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) d\Gamma + \Phi(\mathbf{v}) - \Phi(\mathbf{u}) + \varphi(N\mathbf{v}) - \varphi(N\mathbf{u}) + I_K(\mathbf{v}) - I_K(\mathbf{u}) \geq 0 \text{ for all } \mathbf{v} \in V \tag{35}$$

which implies that $\mathbf{u} \in K$ is a solution to [\(30\)](#).

It suffices to prove that [Problem 5](#) is solvable. To this end, we use [Theorem 1](#). We introduce two operators $T_1, T_2: V \rightarrow 2^{V^*}$ defined by

$$T_1\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{v} + M^*\partial J(M\mathbf{v}, M\mathbf{v}), \quad T_2\mathbf{v} = \partial\Phi(\mathbf{v}) + N^*\partial\varphi(N\mathbf{v}) + \partial I_K(\mathbf{v}) \text{ for } \mathbf{v} \in V.$$

We will verify the that T_1 and T_2 satisfy the hypotheses of [Theorem 1](#).

First, we establish the properties of A . It is easy to see that by $H(\mu)$ (i) and the Hölder inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{A}\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \rangle &= \int_{\Omega} \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{D}\mathbf{v} dx \leq \mu_1 \int_{\Omega} \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{D}\mathbf{v} dx \\ &\leq \mu_1 \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|_{L^2(\Omega, \mathbb{M}^d)} \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\|_{L^2(\Omega, \mathbb{M}^d)} = \mu_1 \|\mathbf{u}\|_V \|\mathbf{v}\|_V \text{ for all } \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in V. \end{aligned}$$

This implies $\|\mathbf{A}\mathbf{u}\|_{V^*} \leq \mu_1 \|\mathbf{u}\|_V$, and therefore A maps bounded sets in V into the bounded sets in V^* , i.e., A is a bounded operator. From hypothesis $H(\mu)$ (ii), it follows

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{A}\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v} \rangle &= \int_{\Omega} (\mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} - \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}) : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}) dx \\ &\geq \mu_2 \int_{\Omega} \|\mathbb{D}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v})\|^2 dx = \mu_2 \|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{v}\|_V^2 \text{ for all } \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in V \end{aligned}$$

and A is a strongly monotone operator. Next, we can use [\[27, Theorem 1.5.2\]](#) (Krasnoselskii’s theorem for the Nemytskii operators) together with $H(\mu)$ (ii) to see that A is bounded and continuous from V to V^* . Since the operator A is bounded, monotone and hemicontinuous (being continuous), by [\[28, Theorem 3.69\(i\)\]](#), we deduce that A is pseudomonotone.

Further, by assumptions $H(j)$, $H(k)$, by [28, Theorem 3.47(v),(vi)], we have

$$\partial J(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u}) \subseteq \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\mathbf{w}) \partial j(\mathbf{u}) d\Gamma \text{ for all } \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u} \in X. \tag{36}$$

which implies

$$\|\partial J(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u})\|_{X^*} \leq c_3 + c_4 \|\mathbf{u}\|_X \text{ for all } \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{u} \in X, \tag{37}$$

where $c_3, c_4 \geq 0$. The latter shows that the operator $\partial J: X \times X \rightarrow 2^{X^*}$ is bounded. Hence T_1 is a bounded operator as a sum of bounded operators.

Next, we check that T_1 is a pseudomonotone operator. The values of T_1 are nonempty, closed and convex subsets of V^* . In fact, the generalized gradient has a nonempty, convex and weakly compact images in X^* , see [28, Proposition 2.23(iv)]. Hence, we deduce that the set $M^* \partial J(M\mathbf{v}, M\mathbf{v})$ is nonempty, closed and convex for all $\mathbf{v} \in V$, and the values of T_1 are nonempty, closed and convex too.

We shall prove that T_1 is a generalized pseudomonotone operator. Let $\mathbf{v}_n \in V$, $\mathbf{v}_n \rightharpoonup \mathbf{v}$ in V , $\mathbf{v}_n^* \in T_1 \mathbf{v}_n$, $\mathbf{v}_n^* \rightharpoonup \mathbf{v}^*$ in V^* and $\limsup \langle \mathbf{v}_n^*, \mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v} \rangle \leq 0$. We will show that $\mathbf{v}^* \in T_1 \mathbf{v}$ and $\langle \mathbf{v}_n^*, \mathbf{v}_n \rangle \rightarrow \langle \mathbf{v}^*, \mathbf{v} \rangle$. By the condition $\mathbf{v}_n^* \in T_1 \mathbf{v}_n$, we have $\mathbf{v}_n^* = A\mathbf{v}_n + M^* \mathbf{w}_n$ with $\mathbf{w}_n \in \partial J(M\mathbf{v}_n, M\mathbf{v}_n)$. It is obvious that $\{\mathbf{w}_n\}$ is bounded in V and $\{M\mathbf{v}_n\}$ is bounded in X . Using the boundedness of ∂J , we obtain that $\{\mathbf{w}_n\}$ remains in a bounded subset of X^* . Hence, by passing to a subsequence, if necessary, we may assume that

$$\mathbf{w}_n \rightharpoonup \mathbf{w} \text{ in } X^* \text{ with } \mathbf{w} \in X^*. \tag{38}$$

On the other hand, by the compactness of operator M , see (12), we deduce that

$$M\mathbf{v}_n \rightarrow M\mathbf{v} \text{ in } X. \tag{39}$$

Taking into account (38), (39) and [28, Proposition 3.23(v)], from $\mathbf{w}_n \in \partial J(M\mathbf{v}_n, M\mathbf{v}_n)$, we have $\mathbf{w} \in \partial J(M\mathbf{v}, M\mathbf{v})$. By passing to the lim sup in the following equality

$$\langle \mathbf{v}_n^*, \mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v} \rangle = \langle A\mathbf{v}_n, \mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v} \rangle + \langle \mathbf{w}_n, M\mathbf{v}_n - M\mathbf{v} \rangle_{X^* \times X},$$

we get

$$\limsup \langle A\mathbf{v}_n, \mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v} \rangle = \limsup \langle \mathbf{v}_n^*, \mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v} \rangle \leq 0.$$

Since A is pseudomonotone, we have

$$A\mathbf{v}_n \rightharpoonup A\mathbf{v} \text{ in } V^* \text{ and } \langle A\mathbf{v}_n, \mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v} \rangle \rightarrow 0.$$

We are now in a position to pass to the limit in the equality $\mathbf{v}_n^* = A\mathbf{v}_n + M^* \mathbf{w}_n$ to get

$$\mathbf{v}^* = A\mathbf{v} + M^* \mathbf{w} \in A\mathbf{v} + M^* \partial J(M\mathbf{v}, M\mathbf{v}) = T_1 \mathbf{v}.$$

Furthermore, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{v}_n^*, \mathbf{v}_n \rangle &= \langle A\mathbf{v}_n, \mathbf{v}_n - \mathbf{v} \rangle + \langle A\mathbf{v}_n, \mathbf{v} \rangle + \langle \mathbf{w}_n, M\mathbf{v}_n \rangle_{X^* \times X} \\ &\rightarrow \langle A\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v} \rangle + \langle \mathbf{w}, M\mathbf{v} \rangle_{X^* \times X} = \langle A\mathbf{v} + M^* \mathbf{w}, \mathbf{v} \rangle = \langle \mathbf{v}^*, \mathbf{v} \rangle. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof that the operator T_1 is generalized pseudomonotone. Since T_1 is a bounded generalized pseudomonotone operator with nonempty, closed and convex values, then T_1 is pseudomonotone, see [27, Proposition 1.3.66].

Next, we shall prove that T_1 is \mathbf{u}_0 -coercive (see Section 2 for the definition) with any $\mathbf{u}_0 \in D(T_2) = K$. Let $\mathbf{u}_0 \in K$ be arbitrary. We prove that

$$\frac{\inf\{\langle \mathbf{u}^*, \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_0 \rangle \mid \mathbf{u}^* \in T_1 \mathbf{u}\}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|_V} \rightarrow +\infty, \text{ as } \|\mathbf{u}\|_V \rightarrow \infty.$$

Let $\mathbf{u} \in V$ and $\mathbf{u}^* \in T_1 \mathbf{u}$. The latter yields $\mathbf{u}^* = A\mathbf{u} + M^* \boldsymbol{\xi}$ with some $\boldsymbol{\xi} \in \partial J(M\mathbf{u}, M\mathbf{u})$ and thus

$$\langle \mathbf{u}^*, \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_0 \rangle = \langle A\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_0 \rangle + \langle \boldsymbol{\xi}, M\mathbf{u} - M\mathbf{u}_0 \rangle_{X^* \times X} = I_1 + I_2.$$

From hypotheses $H(\mu)$, $H(h)$ and (25), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \langle A\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_0 \rangle = \int_{\Omega} (\mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} - \mu(0) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{0}) : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{0}) dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_0 dx + \int_{\Gamma_2} (h(u_v) - h(0)) u_v d\Gamma - \int_{\Gamma_2} h(u_v) u_{0v} d\Gamma \\ &\geq \mu_2 \|\mathbf{u}\|_V^2 - \mu_1 \|\mathbf{u}\|_V \|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V - h_0 \sqrt{|\Gamma_2|} \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V \text{ for all } \mathbf{u} \in V. \end{aligned}$$

As concerns the term I_2 , we can write

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 &= \langle \xi, \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0 \rangle_{X^* \times X} = \langle \partial J(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}), \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0 \rangle_{X^* \times X} \\ &= \langle \partial J(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}) - \partial J(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0), \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0 \rangle_{X^* \times X} \\ &\quad + \langle \partial J(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0), \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0 \rangle_{X^* \times X} =: I_{21} + I_{22} \end{aligned}$$

and we separately estimate I_{21} and I_{22} .

We claim that the functional J defined by (26) satisfies

$$\langle \partial J(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{z}_1) - \partial J(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{z}_2), \mathbf{z}_1 - \mathbf{z}_2 \rangle_{X^* \times X} \geq -k_1 m_j \|\mathbf{z}_1 - \mathbf{z}_2\|_X^2 \tag{40}$$

for all $\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{w} \in X$. To prove the claim, let $\mathbf{z}_1, \mathbf{z}_2, \mathbf{w} \in X$ and $\mathbf{z}_1^* \in \partial J(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{z}_1), \mathbf{z}_2^* \in \partial J(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{z}_2)$. From (36), we deduce that there exists $\xi_i \in X^*$ such that $\xi_i(\mathbf{x}) \in \partial j(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{z}_i(\mathbf{x}))$ for a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$ and

$$\langle \mathbf{z}_i^*, \mathbf{v} \rangle_{X^* \times X} = \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{w}\|) \xi_i(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}) d\Gamma \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{v} \in X$$

for $i = 1, 2$. We observe that hypothesis $H(j)(iv)$ is equivalent, see [42, Lemma 7, p.124], to the following relaxed monotonicity condition of the generalized subgradient

$$\langle \partial j(\mathbf{x}, \xi_1) - \partial j(\mathbf{x}, \xi_2), (\xi_1 - \xi_2) \rangle \geq -m_j \|\xi_1 - \xi_2\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}^2 \quad \text{for all } \xi_1, \xi_2 \in \mathbb{R}^d. \tag{41}$$

The inequality (41) and $H(k)$ imply

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{z}_1^* - \mathbf{z}_2^*, \mathbf{z}_1 - \mathbf{z}_2 \rangle_{X^* \times X} &= \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{w}\|) (\xi_1(\mathbf{x}) - \xi_2(\mathbf{x})) \cdot (\mathbf{z}_1(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{z}_2(\mathbf{x})) d\Gamma \\ &\geq -k_1 m_j \int_{\Gamma_1} \|\mathbf{z}_1(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{z}_2(\mathbf{x})\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}^2 d\Gamma = -k_1 m_j \|\mathbf{z}_1 - \mathbf{z}_2\|_X^2. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the claim (40) follows. Now, from (40) and the inequality

$$\|\mathbf{M}\mathbf{v}\|_X = \|\mathbf{v}_\tau\|_X \leq \|\mathbf{v}\|_X \leq \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{v}\|_V \quad \text{for } \mathbf{v} \in V,$$

we obtain

$$I_{21} \geq -k_1 m_j \|\mathbf{M}\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0\|_X^2 \geq -k_1 m_j \|\gamma\|^2 (\|\mathbf{u}\|_V^2 + \|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V^2 + 2\|\mathbf{u}\|_V \|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V).$$

Let $\bar{\mathbf{u}} \in \partial J(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0), \bar{\mathbf{u}} \in X^*$ be arbitrary. Again we use (36) to infer that there exists $\xi \in X^*$ such that $\xi(\mathbf{x}) \in \partial j(\mathbf{x}, (\mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0)(\mathbf{x}))$ for a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$ and

$$\langle \bar{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{v} \rangle_{X^* \times X} = \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{w}\|) \xi(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}) d\Gamma \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{v} \in X. \tag{42}$$

From $H(j)(iii)$, we can see that

$$\|\xi\|_{X^*} \leq \sqrt{2} (\|c_0\|_{L^2(\Gamma_1)} + c_1 \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V).$$

Hence and by (42), $H(k)$, and the Hölder inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle \bar{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0 \rangle_{X^* \times X}| &\leq k_1 \int_{\Gamma_1} \|\xi(\mathbf{x})\|_{\mathbb{R}^d} \|(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{u})(\mathbf{x}) - (\mathbf{M}\mathbf{u}_0)(\mathbf{x})\|_{\mathbb{R}^d} d\Gamma \\ &\leq k_1 \|\xi\|_{X^*} \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_0\|_V \leq \sqrt{2} k_1 \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_0\|_V (\|c_0\|_{L^2(\Gamma_1)} + c_1 \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V), \end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

and consequently

$$I_{22} \geq -\sqrt{2} k_1 \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_0\|_V (\|c_0\|_{L^2(\Gamma_1)} + c_1 \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V).$$

Finally, we take into account the estimates for I_1, I_{21} , and I_{22} to get

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{u}^*, \mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_0 \rangle &= I_1 + I_2 \geq (\mu_2 - k_1 m_j \|\gamma\|^2) \|\mathbf{u}\|_V^2 - \mu_1 \|\mathbf{u}\|_V \|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V \\ &\quad - k_1 m_j \|\gamma\|^2 (\|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V^2 + 2\|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V \|\mathbf{u}\|_V) - \sqrt{2} k_1 \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_0\|_V (\|c_0\|_{L^2(\Gamma_1)} + c_1 \|\gamma\| \|\mathbf{u}_0\|_V). \end{aligned}$$

By the smallness condition (23), we conclude that T_1 is \mathbf{u}_0 -coercive with any $\mathbf{u}_0 \in K$.

It follows from (27) and (28) that Φ and φ are convex, lower semicontinuous and finite functions, so $D(\partial\Phi) = D(\partial\varphi) = V$. Also, it is well known, see [27, Theorem 1.3.19] that I_K is proper, convex, lower semicontinuous with $D(\partial I_K) = K$. Thus, by [43, Theorem 2.62], the operator T_2 is maximal monotone with $D(T_2) = K$.

Having verified the conditions on T_1 and T_2 , by the surjectivity theorem, we conclude that Problem 5 has a solution, which completes the existence proof of the theorem.

(ii) For the proof of uniqueness, let $\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2 \in K$ be solutions to Problem 3. Then, in the inequality in Problem 3, we choose $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{u}_2$ in the inequality satisfied by \mathbf{u}_1 , and we take $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{u}_1$ in the inequality satisfied by \mathbf{u}_2 . Then we add the resulting inequalities and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} (\mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_1\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_1 - \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_2\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_2) : (\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_1 - \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_2) \, dx \\ & + \int_{\Gamma_2} (h(u_{1\nu}) - h(u_{2\nu})) (u_{1\nu} - u_{2\nu}) \, d\Gamma \\ & \leq \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{u}_{1\tau}\|) j^0(\mathbf{u}_{1\tau}; \mathbf{u}_{2\tau} - \mathbf{u}_{1\tau}) + k(\|\mathbf{u}_{2\tau}\|) j^0(\mathbf{u}_{2\tau}; \mathbf{u}_{1\tau} - \mathbf{u}_{2\tau}) \, d\Gamma. \end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

The term on the right hand side of (44) can be estimated as follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Gamma_1} (k(\|\mathbf{u}_{1\tau}\|) - k(\|\mathbf{u}_{2\tau}\|)) j^0(\mathbf{u}_{1\tau}; \mathbf{u}_{2\tau} - \mathbf{u}_{1\tau}) \\ & + k(\|\mathbf{u}_{2\tau}\|) (j^0(\mathbf{u}_{1\tau}; \mathbf{u}_{2\tau} - \mathbf{u}_{1\tau}) + j^0(\mathbf{u}_{2\tau}; \mathbf{u}_{1\tau} - \mathbf{u}_{2\tau})) \, d\Gamma \\ & \leq L_j L_k \|\gamma\|^2 \|\mathbf{u}_1 - \mathbf{u}_2\|_V^2 + k_1 m_j \|\gamma\|^2 \|\mathbf{u}_1 - \mathbf{u}_2\|_V^2. \end{aligned}$$

Here we have used the fact that $j(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$ is Lipschitz with constant $L_j > 0$ for a.e. $\mathbf{x} \in \Gamma_1$ if and only if $\|\partial j(\xi)\|_{\mathbb{R}^d} \leq L_j$ for all $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^d$. We combine the last inequality with $H(h)(ii)$, $H(\mu)(ii)$ and (44) to deduce

$$(\mu_2 - (k_1 m_j + L_j L_k) \|\gamma\|^2) \|\mathbf{u}_1 - \mathbf{u}_2\|_V^2 \leq 0.$$

Finally, from (24), we deduce $\mathbf{u}_1 = \mathbf{u}_2$, which completes the proof of (ii).

We pass to the proof of (iii). Let $\{\mu_n\}, \mu \in \mathcal{M}$. By step (ii), the unique solutions $\mathbf{u}_n, \mathbf{u} \in K$ of Problem 3 corresponding to μ_n and μ , respectively, are well defined. We have the following two inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \mu_n(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}_n) \, dx + \int_{\Gamma_2} h(u_{n\nu})(v_\nu - u_{n\nu}) \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{u}_{n\tau}\|) j^0(\mathbf{u}_{n\tau}; \mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_{n\tau}) \, d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_3} (\phi(v_\nu) - \phi(u_{n\nu})) \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{g}(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\| - \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n\|) \, dx \geq \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}_n) \, dx, \\ & \int_{\Omega} \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} : \mathbb{D}(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) \, dx + \int_{\Gamma_2} h(u_\nu)(v_\nu - u_\nu) \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|) j^0(\mathbf{u}_\tau; \mathbf{v}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_\tau) \, d\Gamma + \int_{\Gamma_3} (\phi(v_\nu) - \phi(u_\nu)) \, d\Gamma \\ & + \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{g}(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{v}\| - \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \, dx \geq \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{f} \cdot (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{u}) \, dx \end{aligned}$$

for all $\mathbf{v} \in K$. We select $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{u}$ in the first inequality and $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{u}_n$ in the second one, and next we add the resulting inequalities to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} (\mu_n(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n - \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}) : (\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}) \, dx \\ & + \int_{\Gamma_2} (h(u_{n\nu}) - h(u_\nu)) (u_{n\nu} - u_\nu) \, d\Gamma \\ & \leq \int_{\Gamma_1} k(\|\mathbf{u}_{n\tau}\|) j^0(\mathbf{u}_{n\tau}; \mathbf{u}_\tau - \mathbf{u}_{n\tau}) + k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|) j^0(\mathbf{u}_\tau; \mathbf{u}_{n\tau} - \mathbf{u}_\tau) \, d\Gamma. \end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

By a similar argument as in the part (ii), from $H(h)(ii)$, $H(\mu)(ii)$ and (45), we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} (\mu_n(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n - \mu_n(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}) : (\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}) \, dx \\ & + \int_{\Omega} (\mu_n(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} - \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}) : (\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}) \, dx \\ & \leq k_1 m_j \|\gamma\|^2 \|\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbf{u}\|_V^2 + L_j L_k \|\gamma\|^2 \|\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbf{u}\|_V^2. \end{aligned}$$

We use $H(\mu)$ (ii) and the Hölder inequality to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & (\mu_2 - (k_1 m_j + L_j L_k) \|\gamma\|^2) \|\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbf{u}\|_V^2 \\ & \leq \left(\int_{\Omega} [\mu_n(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u} - \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}]^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \left(\int_{\Omega} \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \end{aligned}$$

which yields

$$(\mu_2 - (k_1 m_j + L_j L_k) \|\gamma\|^2) \|\mathbf{u}_n - \mathbf{u}\|_V \leq \left(\int_{\Omega} |\mu_n(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) - \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|)|^2 \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|^2 dx \right)^{1/2}. \tag{46}$$

By the assumption $H(\mu)$ (i), we can assert that

$$|\mu_n(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) - \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|)|^2 \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|^2 \leq (\mu_1 - \mu_0)^2 \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|^2$$

which together with the pointwise convergence of μ_n to μ , by the Lebesgue dominated convergence theorem, gives

$$\int_{\Omega} |\mu_n(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|) - \mu(\|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|)|^2 \|\mathbb{D}\mathbf{u}\|^2 dx \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Finally, by the smallness condition (24), the inequality (46) entails $\mathbf{u}_n \rightarrow \mathbf{u}$ in V , as $n \rightarrow \infty$, which completes the proof of the theorem. \square

The results (i) and (ii) of Theorem 4 on existence and uniqueness of solution provide a generalization of [41, Theorem 18].

5. An inverse coefficient problem

The goal of this section is to establish the main result on the existence of solution to the inverse coefficient problem. In this context Problem 3 is called the direct problem.

We consider the following optimal control problem. The role of control is played by a viscosity function and the admissible set of coefficients is denoted by $\mathcal{M}_{ad} \subset \mathcal{M}$.

Problem 6. Find a viscosity function $\mu^* \in \mathcal{M}_{ad}$ such that

$$F(\mathbf{u}(\mu^*)) \leq F(\mathbf{u}(\mu)) \text{ for all } \mu \in \mathcal{M}_{ad}, \tag{47}$$

where $F: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an objective functional, and $\mathbf{u}(\mu) \in K \subset V$, for $\mu \in \mathcal{M}$, represents the unique solution to Problem 3 corresponding to the parameter μ .

We need the following hypotheses.

$H(\mathcal{M}_{ad})$: The admissible set $\mathcal{M}_{ad} \subset \mathcal{M}$ of functions is equicontinuous, that is, for a given $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $\delta > 0$ such that for each $\mu \in \mathcal{M}_{ad}$, it holds $|\mu(r) - \mu(s)| \leq \varepsilon$ for all $r, s \in [0, \infty)$ with $|r - s| \leq \delta$.

$H(F)$: $F: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is sequentially lower semicontinuous.

Theorem 7. Assume the hypotheses of Theorem 4(iii), $H(\mathcal{M}_{ad})$, and $H(F)$. Then Problem 6 has a solution.

Proof. Let $\{\mu_n\}$ be a minimizing sequence for Problem 6, i.e., $\mu_n \in \mathcal{M}_{ad}$ and

$$F(\mathbf{u}(\mu_n)) \rightarrow \inf\{F(\mathbf{u}(\mu)) \mid \mu \in \mathcal{M}_{ad}\}, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

The set of admissible parameters \mathcal{M}_{ad} is equibounded and equicontinuous, thus we are in a position to apply the Ascoli-Arzelà theorem. We deduce that there is a subsequence of μ_n , we do not relabel, and a function $\mu^* \in \mathcal{M}_{ad}$ such that μ_n converges uniformly on any compact subset of $[0, \infty)$ to μ^* . By Theorem 4(iii), it follows that $\mathbf{u}_n = \mathbf{u}(\mu_n) \in K$ converges in V to $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}(\mu^*) \in K$. Taking into account $H(F)$, we infer that

$$F(\mathbf{u}(\mu^*)) \leq \liminf F(\mathbf{u}(\mu_n)) = \inf\{F(\mathbf{u}(\mu)) \mid \mu \in \mathcal{M}_{ad}\}$$

which completes the proof. \square

The reasonable examples of the cost functional which are interesting from the physical point of view are (1) and the following:

$$F_1(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \|\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{u}_d\|^2 dx$$

which measures the deviation of the velocity of the fluid from a given target velocity $\mathbf{u}_d \in L^2(\Omega; \mathbb{R}^d)$,

$$F_2(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \|\text{curl } \mathbf{u}\|^2 dx$$

which describes the vorticity of the velocity field, and

$$F_3(\mathbf{u}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} \|\mathbb{D} \mathbf{u}\|^2 dx$$

which is the rate dissipation energy (or drug) function and measures the drug due to viscosity. It can be shown that these functionals satisfy $H(F)$.

We conclude this section with an example of a potential function j which satisfies hypothesis $H(j)$, for simplicity we skip the dependence on the spatial variable. Let $j: \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be defined by

$$j(\xi) = (\alpha - 1)e^{-\|\xi\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}} + \alpha \|\xi\|_{\mathbb{R}^d} \text{ for } \xi \in \mathbb{R}^d$$

with a constant $\alpha \in [0, 1)$. Then, the generalized gradient has the form

$$\partial j(\xi) = \begin{cases} \bar{B}(\mathbf{0}, 1), & \text{if } \xi = \mathbf{0}, \\ \left((1 - \alpha)e^{-\|\xi\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}} + \alpha \right) \frac{\xi}{\|\xi\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}}, & \text{if } \xi \neq \mathbf{0} \end{cases} \text{ for } \xi \in \mathbb{R}^d,$$

where $\bar{B}(\mathbf{0}, 1)$ denotes the closed unit ball in \mathbb{R}^d . The function j is nonconvex and $\|\partial j(\xi)\|_{\mathbb{R}^d} \leq 1$ for all $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^d$. Further, it satisfies $H(j)$ with $c_0 = 1$, $c_1 = \mathbf{0}$ and $m_j = 1$, and j is Lipschitz continuous with constant one.

The case $\alpha = 1$ leads to the convex function $j(\xi) = \|\xi\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}$ for $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^d$. Then, the second condition in (6) is of the form

$$-\tau_\tau(\mathbf{u}) \in k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|) \partial \|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|_{\mathbb{R}^d} \text{ on } \Gamma_1$$

which is equivalent to a version of slip-dependent condition of frictional type

$$\begin{cases} \|\tau_\tau\| \leq k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|), & \text{if } \mathbf{u}_\tau = \mathbf{0} \\ \tau_\tau = -k(\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|) \frac{\mathbf{u}_\tau}{\|\mathbf{u}_\tau\|_{\mathbb{R}^d}}, & \text{if } \mathbf{u}_\tau \neq \mathbf{0} \end{cases} \text{ on } \Gamma_1.$$

Further, for any convex function $j(\mathbf{x}, \cdot)$, we have $m_j = 0$. In this case the smallness condition (23) holds.

6. Final comment

It would be interesting to address the following open issues related to the results of this paper. First it is of interest to recover the pressure from the variational–hemivariational inequality in the direct problem, Problem 3, see [15]. Also, an interesting topic is to extend the results to Navier–Stokes equation instead of the Stokes equation. Next, it seems to be a hard problem to derive and examine the necessary conditions of optimality for the control problem (47). Finally, it is an extensive and important project to study the numerical analysis of the direct problem and the inverse one.

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